

Question	Code	Description
Demographic	Q1	Consent
	Q2	Student or staff
	Q3	Student type
	Q4	Staff type
	Year	Year of data collection
To what extent do you agree that researchers in the University have the expertise to deliver on ...	Q15	Open science – (Engaging in other open science practices over the research lifecycle, e.g., open research data, open peer review, open source, open code, making research materials & methods openly available)
	Q24	Open science – (Specifically, publishing outputs via open access)
	Q25	Research integrity (e.g., good authorship practice, robust study design, data analysis, reporting, etc.) ²
	Q28	Valuing quality of research outputs over quantity
	Q29	Providing support to peers or colleagues
	Q32	Collaborate across functions or disciplines
To what extent do you agree with the following statements?	Q8	Statement 1: I feel comfortable approaching colleagues in the University for research mentorship, advice, or peer review.
	Q9	Statement 2: I understand what constitutes good authorship practice in my discipline.
	Q10	Statement 3: I understand what constitutes research impact in my discipline.
	Q11	Statement 4: I have access to the appropriate resources/infrastructure to support good research practice.
	Q12	Statement 5: I have the appropriate support during the grant application process.
	Q13	Statement 6: I feel able to spend time undertaking Continuing Professional Development activities that are relevant to my career aspirations.
	Q14	Statement 7: I know where to go to report a potential case of Unacceptable Research Practice or Research Misconduct.
I know where in the University I can go for information or support on:	Q16	Research Data Management
	Q17	Research Integrity
	Q18	Research Ethics
	Q19	Open Science – (Specifically, publishing outputs via open access)
	Q20	Good Authorship Practice
	Q21	Open Science Practices
	Q22	How research quality is assessed in my discipline
	Q23	Improving my research profile
Rank the following in order of importance	Q26	
Have you participated in research related training in the past two years?	Training	